

Guidelines for the annotation of evaluation datasets from art-historical texts for Artwork-centric Knowledge Extraction (Art-KE)

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Introduction: Object-centric Knowledge Extraction is a fundamental task for Art-historical texts, since most of the discourses present in these texts are about events concerning the realization of some artifacts. However, if entities extracted by Knowledge Extraction tools are often defined via proper names or phrasal constituents which have a *referential* rather than *descriptive* nature (e.g., proper names), artifacts are complex objects which are more often described in texts using several attributes which have distinct linguistic features (creator, subject, material, etc.).

T1: Sequence Labelling with Artwork-centric Classes

This task consists in identifying in-text references to entities which are related to the production, preservation or maintenance of an artifact. Prerequisite in the annotation of these entities is that they are referenced along with the artifact in the same proposition. For the sake of clarity, we distinguish between core-entities, subclasses and non-core entities. Moreover, to further define which phrasal constituents are annotated for each class, we defined four annotation layers: *Generic*, *Named Entity*, *Iconography* and *Time Expression*.

1. Core entities

Class	Layer	Description	Example
Agent	Named Entity	Named entities which act as creator or secondary agent in the event of creation of a work.	Verrocchio, Leonardo, Donatello, Michelangelo
Artifact	Generic	Result of human activity which is considered creative and requires effort or labor.	work of art, copy, picture, book
Title	Named Entity	Proper name which is used to identify a specific man-made work. From this class are excluded names of artistic themes used in an <i>ekphrasis</i> , i.e. written description of a work of art, while names of buildings are included.	Cathedral of Notre Dame, Birth of Venus, Old Testament, Madonna and Child, Vitruvian Man.
Represented	Iconography	objects, entities, themes and motifs depicted in a work, which can occur in its title or in an <i>ekphrasis</i>	S. Peter, a nude David, head, book, Adoration of the Magi, grotesque
State of represented	Iconography	Phrasal constituents which predicate specific attributes of the represented.	[Mary] _{rep} [standing with many angels above her] _{state}

Time of action	Time expression	Expressions which refer either to one specific date, a duration or a date interval related to the creation or maintenance of an artifact.	in 1984, between 1250 and 1253, after the death of Cosimo, in the next year
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2. Artifact subclasses

Class	Layer	Description	Example
Visual Work	Generic	Works which are created or arranged and are primarily perceived by the sense of sight, such as paintings and sculptures.	painting, sculpture, statue, figure, representation, model, design, drawing
Built work	Generic	Works which refer to single buildings and facilities which are man-made and have an aesthetic value.	church, palace, temple, bridge, gate.
Furnishing and Equipment	Generic	Objects that are primarily movable that provide comfort, convenience, or protection in dwellings, places or business, or other public or private spaces.	helmet, crest, couch, chair, organ, clock
Component	Generic	Components of works, such as architectural elements or constituents of structures and visual works.	pier, architrave, column, basement, predella, slab, altar, chapel, room, window.

3. Non-core entities

Class	Layer	Description	Example
Material	Generic	Material from which artifacts are composed.	marble, oil, wood, soil, glass.
Place	Named Entity	Natural places or Geo-political entities which identify the location of a work.	New York, Rome, Seine, Alps
Technique	Generic	Techniques from which works are made.	Fresco, low-relief, plating

Reference	Named Entity	A representation of the entity depicted which the Creator uses as a reference in the creation of the artifact.	copy of the [portrait of Pope Leo X] _{reference}
Style and Period	Generic	Art and architecture styles, historical periods, art movements, nationalities, ethnicities, and culture related to artistic endeavors.	ancient, Renaissance Art, Florentine
Beneficiary	Named Entity	Patrons and Organizations which benefit from the creation or maintenance of an artifact	Cosimo de Medici, Sixtus IV, Congregation of Camaldoli

4. Lexical characteristics of annotation layers

Generic concepts: Artifacts, Style and Period, Material, Technique

Usually terms referring to generic concepts are expressed with common nouns, more rarely with noun phrases (*silver plating, Corinthian order*). For this layer, the annotation considers just the lexical units which occur in fine-art thesauri. This means that adjectives or numerals which express additional information are left unannotated.

- Giovanni of Pisa designed the <component>façade<component> of the <built_work>Duomo<built_work> with three principal <component>doors<component>.

Named entities: Agent, Place, Title, Reference, Beneficiary

These entities usually consist of proper names, rarely of noun phrases (*School of Athens, Nuns of S. Jacopo, house of Medici*). Named entities may contain toponyms (*Leonardo da Vinci*), patronymics (*Michelangelo di Lodovico di Buonarroti*), epithets and temporal roles (*Ser Brunelleschi, King Julius*) and appositives (*Antonino, Archbishop of Florence*).

Titles and References are further special cases. Titles are usually identifiable by the presence of double-quotes, capitalized words or definite articles. References may or may not contain titles. However, it's important that they unambiguously refer to a piece of work.

- <beneficiary>Pope Leo</beneficiary> commissioned the <title><component>Chamber</component> of Our Lady at <place>Loreto</place></title> to <agent>Maestro Andrea Contucci of Monte Sansovino</agent>.
- This is stated in his <artifact>book</artifact> <title>"De Asse"</title> and in his <artifact>observations</artifact> on <reference>the Pandects</reference>.

- a <artifact>copy</artifact> of <reference>the picture in which Raffaello had formerly painted portraits of Pope Leo X, Cardinal Giulio de' Medici and Cardinal de' Rossi</reference>.

Iconography: Represented and State of Represented

These categories are used to define iconographic subjects. Represented entities are usually referenced via common or proper nouns. States of represented are usually verb phrases which depict the state in which the represented is usually depicted. While the annotation of represented entities follows the same rules of generic concepts and named entities, state of represented may include long phrasal structures whose only boundary is the proposition end.

- He depicted <represented₁>Our Lady</represented₁> <state_of_represented₁>standing, raised from the <represented₂>ground</represented₂> on a <represented₃>pedestal</represented₃>, and uplifting her <represented₄>head</represented₄> towards <represented₅>Heaven</represented₅></state_of_represented₁>.

T2. Resolution using Controlled Vocabularies and Knowledge Graphs

In order to add semantics to the terms and entities extracted in **T1**, these should be mapped to unique entries in a thesaurus or Knowledge Graph. In specific:

- **Generic concepts** (Artifacts, Visual Works, Built Works, Components, Materials, Techniques, Styles and Periods) should be mapped to the respective terms in the AAT hierarchy. For example the term “church” is mapped to the entry <churches (buildings), 300007466>.
- **Named entities** (Agents, Titles, Places, Beneficiaries) are linked to entries in Wikidata, which acts as a general-purpose encyclopedia.
- **Iconography terms** which define represented entities and their states are described using Iconclass notations. For example in “David holding the head of Goliath”, “A nude David” is resolved to the Iconclass notation <11I62(DAVID), David (not in biblical context)> while the state “holding the head of Goliath” is resolved to <71H145, David with Goliath’s head>.

The only layer which does not consider a resolution step is the Time Expression layer. In each other layer, if a sequence cannot be linked to any term in the considered thesaurus or KB, the default null value is `NIL`.

Exceptions and special cases for T1 and T2

- 1) Multiple identifiers for a concept or entity

An entity may correspond to two entities in a vocabulary or Knowledge Graph which are semantically equivalent. When it is not possible to determine which one is more suitable,

both are considered as valid answers. For example, the term “work” used in the English translation of Vasari has two equivalent concepts in the AAT hierarchy: “works (general, creative) [300387357]” and “works of art [300133025]”. More exceptions will be added in the future versions of this documentation.

T3 Relation extraction

This section will be filled in the next version of the documentation.

Evaluation strategy

This section will be filled in the next version of the documentation.